

Khaybar Desert Kites

Desert and Harrat landscapes of Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Siria and Iraq are covered with strange man made prehistoric structures, named desert kites. It may be that the naming is not most appropriate. But at the time I will keep on using this name as it appears it is quite common. These structures are enigmatic. They are huge, sometimes spanning kilometres of now barren deserts. There is no doubt that they are old. Very old.

Some scholars date them to Neolithic period, some to chalcolithic or even younger. But there is no doubt that these structures are prehistoric. No scientific proof or research on the dating of these structures is know to me. But that may be just my lack of knowledge.

There was much discussion about the meaning of these structures. But most scholars agree that they were used as hunting traps, to herd game in the ending enclosure of the kite.

In this paper I want to discuss some less known desert kites, namely from Harrat Khaybar area in Saudi Arabia.

Harrat Khaybar is a lava plateau in NW Saudi Arabia. It spans across 14.000 square kilometres. What is now barren black desert of volcanic stone and sand was some time ago covered with bush and green pastures. My focus here is western edge of Harrat, near the oasis of Khaybar and Ash Shurayf . To cover the whole area of Harrat Khaybar would be a task that would require years of work and probably several books, just to catalogue and describe the area.

Khaybar area was settled from prehistoric times. One can find literally thousands of prehistoric and ancient settlements, burial structures, simple cairns, cities, corals and single houses, farms. Area is so rich with prehistoric monuments that we can characterise it as one of prehistoric centres of culture. I believe it is unique on the planet. To my knowledge it is one of rare prehistoric sites where one can walk the roads and streets of prehistoric villages, enter the yards and houses, rooms of prehistoric people. Without even move a single shovel of dirt. It is uniquely preserved. A complete prehistoric landscape frozen in time.

This is the area where we can find desert kites. They are positioned on the east and west of oasis, on the lava plateau. They are often opened with their wide funnel shaped entrance towards the valley .

Kite shapes

Kites are basically triangular shapes with one end opened. Shahmon desert kite in Negev desert is a good example of very simple basic shape of the kite.

It consist of two converging more or less straight walls, that create funnel shape which ends with narrow passage to a sort of coral enclosure. Typically there are two three or more circular enclosures on the edge of this coral.

Kites can be and often are much more complex in shapes. And sizes vary. From smaller few hundred meters in length to huge kites that can span over several kilometres in length. Typical more complex shape of kite would incorporate 5 or more circular enclosures joint with curve shaped walls. And more than one leading wall, creating the funnel to herd the game in the ending enclosure.

This is very nice sample from Syria Note that there are several converging walls leading to the ending enclosure area. Area is surrounded with 5 small circular structures. And walls connecting them are shaped in small funnels leading to each one of them. Circular shape in the upper right corner is prehistoric farm.
Kites can form even more complex shapes.
This example is from the Khaybar area.

We can see that several kite shapes are combined together to create one bigger kite. And even two or more different kites are joined and coordinated in the landscape to create quite complex structures.

But all kites have a basic distinctive shape. Funnel shaped leading walls ending with closed space with one or more circular structure attached to it.

Function

We have plenty of archaeological evidence that define these structures as hunting traps. Many rock art images represent the function of these structures.

Here are two rock art images from Syrian desert that clearly depict herding of game in these kite like structures.

But just simplistic conclusion does not provide a complete answer.

If one would look carefully at the remains of desert kites in the field, you would notice that these 'walls' that lead to ending enclosure are much too low to be able to stop any game at all. Even small animals like rabbits could easily jump over these walls. Even if we take in consideration that walls are much ruined. There is simply not enough material lying around the walls to build them even meter high. And a fence of a meter stone wall would not stop antelope or wild goat to jump over it. Apparently these walls are not walls at all. Note the lower portion of image on the right. It seems that it is not a stone wall that is depicted, but rather a fence made of branches, poles and twigs. That would make much more sense in terms of economy to build these structures as well as functionality.

In a rocky desert of Harrats one would have much trouble to stick a pole in the ground. Ground is hard and rocky. If you want to build a fence made of wooden poles and branches you have only one solution. To put a pole in upright position and fix it with stones around its base. If you continue to do that in line every feet or two feet, you will eventually end with something that would look like stone wall, but it is not. It is a line of stones used to fix wooden poles and branches upright.

Another important factor would be known to everyone ever herding goats. Goat is an animal very capable to jump and even climb steep rocks and cliffs. The same is true for antelope. Only two meter high wall would stop a goat or antelope. Anything below this would not be effective. But a fence made of poles and branches would most definitely stop antelope or goat. These animals avoid thick bush by nature. To them, very thick bush is a trap where they could entangle in branches or even be impaled on in case of trying to jump over.

Every goat keeper in Africa knows that. They construct simple fences out of entangled branches of thorn bush. Sometimes these fences even stop bigger predators like lions to attack the flock.

Building two meters high stone wall would result in enormous amount of work. Plus there would be clear evidence of large heaps of stone rubble today. But there is none. The amount of stone in near vicinity of these 'walls' would not be sufficient for 1 m high wall. And in the case of drywall, if you double the height you quadruple the volume of material needed. So clearly these leading walls of desert kites re actually not walls at all, but stones that where used to support poles and probably thorn branches used to construct a fence. Of course any wooden material is long gone and would not survive millenniums.

But what is the real nature and function of these hunting traps? Apparently ancient people used them to herd wild goats or antelopes in them. To slaughter them? How effective where these installations? How many people used them? Who and when?

We can answer at least some of these questions. To my firm believe these hunting traps where not designed to just capture and then kill animals. For that you could design much simpler hunting trap. The ending part of desert kites is crucial in these interpretations. A simple funnel shaped enclosure with ending circular trap would be sufficient for the task. Something like this.

Hunters would herd the game in the funnel and in the circular trap at the end. Close the narrow passage with braches, or just take a stand there. And the slaughter could begin.

But as we have seen in desert kites are much more complex than this. Ending enclosures are carefully shaped and have usually more than one small circular building attached to it. Even if we try to interpret these small circular structures as storage for meat of shelter for hunters that would not explain elaborate work in shaping ending enclosures. And more than one circular hut at the perimeter and evenly spaced apart does not make any sense.

There is something that is very obvious.

Let us look at this detail in some of the kites.

Note the curved line of wall between two circular huts. This is intentional. It would be much more simple and less work to make a straight wall between both circular huts if you just want to close the area.

But someone in the past made more effort to build much longer and elaborate structure. It took him more time and material. But I guess he knew exactly what was he doing.

Here is another example. Lines connecting these circular huts are curved so that we get a shape of another small funnel. And there is only one reason for that extra effort and shape.

They herded game in the larger enclosure at the end of the kite. Then they selected animals and distributed herded them in these circular huts or building at the periphery of the enclosure.

A funnel like shape of walls divided the area in distinctive small traps, each ending with one or two circular building. If they would intend to kill all animals, there would be no reason to herd them further in these small circular buildings. These building have a typical size of 3 to 5 meters in diameter. And once game was captured in these small buildings it could not escape. Note that these buildings have actually proper wall that was much higher then the so called 'walls' of the funnel. The amount of rubble around them (thickness of dark line in aerial photos) suggest that these were actually built walls of some meter and a half in height. Not enough for a family of prehistoric hunters to live in, but enough to keep a small number of 6 or 10 animals trapped and closed.

Why would ancient hunters do that?

The answer is really very simple. In time when there was no deep freeze and refrigerators, when conservation of food was difficult, one option to have fresh meat for longer period is to keep it alive. Yes. They kept captured goats or antelopes in these small circular huts and used them for food when necessary. If they would kill all captured animals at once, they would have to eat them at once or meat would spoil. But they figured that they can keep captured game for weeks alive in these small huts. All they had to do is provide water and maybe some food to animals. And a family of hunters could live from the game that they captured in these kite like traps for weeks. Of course the animals would eventually loose body weight. But that would more or less account to loss of fat. Not muscle tissue.

What we have here is evidently first attempt of domestication of animals. And that is of much importance. Not only does these desert kites tell us when. But they tell us story of the process of domestication in detail.

We probably do not speak of real domestication. But a step between hunting and organised intentional raising of animals. Animals captured in these hunting traps where wild. Probably antelopes. But a process of keeping them alive to provide fresh meat or maybe even milk for the family is first step in domestication. Someone has to provide these animals at least water to drink or they would perish within few days.

From the elaborate shape of desert kites we can clearly see that they would be used not just for hunting the game as that would allow for much simpler structures. But that these structures were used to keep hunted animals alive at least for some time.

That is very important moment in history of mankind.

But we did not yet find answer to the following question. If they used these structures to hunt and then keep animals, why do these hunting structures have five, eight or even more circular structures? Would it not be simpler and more economical to make one bigger circular hut?

Yes and no.

One thing we have to consider is that making a bigger circular hut to keep wild game entrapped, would require much more work. It is a fact that if you want to keep something so intelligent as goat or antelope trapped you would have to cover the roof of these buildings with thorn bushes or some other firm structure that would deter animals from jumping or climbing out of the pens. If you make a building with larger diameter, a task to roof it over and keep animals trapped is much harder. So it would be better to make one or two smaller pens, then big one.

But on the other hand we can see often that desert kites have groups of these circular pens arranged around the trap enclosure. Sometimes we have two or three pens one to another, then another two or three on the other end of the enclosure.

Several pens one next to other can be explained by simplicity of the structure. It would be easier to build two smaller pens then one larger. And also keeping and controlling animals in smaller groups is much easier. But that does not explain why there are two three or more such groups of pens at one enclosure.

Reason for having more than one group of circular pens in enclosure is in economy.

Building of simple desert kite some 200 meters long is quite a task. It would take several people two weeks or more to build, including pens at the terminal enclosure. But we have often desert kites that are huge and spread kilometres in length. Some are very elaborate and carefully built.

It is obvious that such a task is more than one family can handle. Even if we consider prehistoric families to be much larger than today, it is still enormous project.

Several families have to be involved in such a task. While some people took care of daily jobs, food and children, others built these enormous desert kites, that would provide food for the family in future. Most probably it was not even a task of one generation. And it looks that some desert kites have grown and evolved from simpler to more complex structure through the work of several generations.

If we consider that more than one family was involved in building these structures then more than one family was involved in using them. That would explain several groups of circular pens. Each family would use the common hunting trap and then store, keep captured animals in it's own set of pens.

Another possible explanation is that desert kites were used often. And when one set of circular pens would be full, next batch of captured game would be enclosed in another set. Yet that would not explain why these sets of pens would be distributed around the perimeter of enclosure. It would be much simpler to construct one funnel shaped terminal enclosure with enough sets of circular pens to house all captured animals.

One thing is certain. These constructions and usage of them would not be possible without organised collaborative effort. Only organised society with work division and some sort of formal organisation is capable of constructing such monumental structures. Another important factor is that these structures were not made by completely nomadic people. People that build them had to settle in the area at least for the time of building these structures. That would be typically several month, regarding average size and complexity of desert kites. And after the work on building these hunting traps, they would often come back to the same places to use them. Also keeping the animals alive in pens would require some attendance.

So we can conclude that desert kites were built by people who settled the area for a considerable amount of time or maybe moved between two or three locations seasonally. And it is interesting to notice that in the Khaybar area and some parts of Black Desert in Syria we have remains of Neolithic villages very close to the hunting desert kites. But linking desert kites with remains of houses and villages only a few hundred meters away would be an error.

Wild animals avoid places where people live. Wherever people live, there is unusual noise, smell of fire, fear ... Yet all these kites are so close to prehistoric settlements. But a more careful look will reveal some important details.

Khaybar area is full with ancient burial structures. Sometimes in form of small simple cairn, sometimes more elaborate burial cairn with stone circle around it or maybe even leading trail of stones or stone wall leading to it.

But we will often find these cairns inside desert kites. I believe that to anyone so respectful to its dead relatives it would be a severe offence to herd wild game over the grave of its father or grandfather. We can conclude that these burial mounds are from a much later period.

Note keyhole shaped burial mounds aligned along the path/road that cuts the desert kite. On the top of image you can even see one of circular pens to be reused as burial cairn.

We can associate these burial structures aligned with roads connecting villages and cities in Khaybar area. But desert kites are much older than these villages. Most of the settlements of Khaybar are on the very edge of fertile valley. And most of the kites in the area are orientated with its wider open side towards the valley. Sometimes beginning just 100m from the edge of the village. Both could not be in use at the same time. And closer examination of burial structures around Khaybar area will reveal several layers of these structures probably spanning from Neolithic to iron age.

Top image on page 2 clearly show Neolithic farm very close to the kite enclosure. Another kite in the vicinity of former one looks like this.

Neolithic house, huts, pens for animals and yards are overlaying and disturbing remains of desert kite.

We can place the beginning of these desert kites at the very beginning of Neolithic period. In time when people settled and started to domesticate animals. I won't set even approximate dating here for that can be 1000 or 2000 years apart for Syria comparing to Khaybar. At the moment I think exact dating is somehow irrelevant. More important is the knowledge that desert kites can give us good look in the moment when animal domestication began. A look in the complexity and organisation of that society that used knowledge and skill to provide more or less constant source of meat and milk.

We must consider that the face of Saudi Arabia changed significantly from those times. What is today arid desert sand was once fertile enough to provide vegetation and water to herds of gazelles. One glimpse in particular spot can tell you much. Use Google Earth application and look at lat: 29.183335 lon: 39.580291. Zoom in to eye altitude of 892 meters. And you will find faint remains of desert kite in the midst of sand dunes of terrible Nafud desert. For someone to build desert kite in that particular spot, it must have been worth the effort. 8.2 kiloyear Bond event can be considered as terminal time line for desert kites. That was global climate change that started to change Nafud to what it is now. Arid plane of sand dunes.

So at least some of desert kites could be older than 8.500 years BP.

More systematic research should be done on the subject. So far desert kites were considered just strange archaeological phenomena. But as we have found out are more than just significant. They are crucial evidence in the one of most important events in history of mankind.

A lot of work can be done even with some rudimentary data as Google Earth. Systematic catalogue of desert kites is necessary. And further comparative analysis and most probably some field work to confirm further theories.

It is a task for a team of people. I invite all amateurs, archaeologists, scholars and anyone interested to contact me. Maybe we can make a working team, that would do some undestructive archaeology from home computer. Maybe we will manage to kick start archaeological community to start thinking and to pressure governments of regarding countries to protect those monuments of human history.

At least I hope you learned that by simple logical thinking one can learn more from simple and scarce evidence.

Vanja Janežič